

Research Article

Genetic investigation of virulence factors genes among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from clinical sources

Mohammedbaqeri Hayder Alkam Thebhawe¹ and Nabil Salim Saaid Tuwaij^{1*}¹Department of Biology Faculty of Science, University of Kufa, Iraq.*Corresponding author: nabeel.tuwaij@uokufa.edu.iq**Article Info****Keywords:** *lasA*, *pilA*, virulence factors gene, *nan-1***Received:** 06.03.2025**Accepted:** 21.05.2025**Published:** 12.06.2025 © 2025 by the author's. The terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license apply to this open access article.**Abstract**

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is considered one of the most common causes of infection, especially in immunocompromised patients. Therefore, this study aimed to detect the virulence factor genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates. The isolates were collected from different sources: 18/100 (18%) burn patients, 13/100 (13%) diabetic foot ulcer patients, and 2/100 (2%) patients suffering from urinary tract infections. The growth rate of Gram-positive bacteria was 79 (26.33%), while the rate of Gram-negative bacteria was 168 (56%). Results of antibiotic susceptibility showed that the highest bacterial resistance was Cefepime 33(100%) while the least resistance was Meropenem reached 16(48.48%). Results of Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) showed that 29 (87.87%), 9 (27.27%), 29(87.87%), 33(100%), 33(100%) and 17(51.51%) of *P. aeruginosa* isolates had *pilB*, *pilA*, *lasA*, *lasB*, *algD*, and *nan-1* genes, respectively in this work.

1. Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (*P. aeruginosa*) is one of the most clinically important Gram-negative bacteria. It is an opportunistic pathogen responsible for about 10 to 20% of nosocomial infections worldwide [1], virulence factors are components that allow an organism to infect a host and are often responsible for patient symptoms [2] *P. aeruginosa* has many virulence factors enzymes and toxins which disrupt host cells and aid bacterial invasion [3] flagella, which are involved in swimming motility within liquid environments [4] pili, which play a role in adhesion to cells and surfaces, biofilm formation, and gene transfer [5]. A distinctive hallmark of *P. aeruginosa* is its propensity for biofilm formation, an intricate process wherein bacterial cells aggregate within a self-produced extracellular matrix. This biofilm formation encompasses a complex architectural arrangement that renders the bacterium impervious to conventional antibiotic regimens and contributes significantly to its clinical impact [6].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Ethical approval

Official approvals were obtained to take samples from patients in health institutions, as well as the patients' consent, in addition to following all procedures and instructions recommended by the University of Kufa, College of Science.

3.2. Antimicrobial susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

The results of the current study showed high resistance by *P. aeruginosa* isolates to an important group of drugs, where the highest resistance was recorded to the antibiotic Cefepime, and Netilmicin, which reached 100%, followed by resistance to antibiotics Netilmicin and which reached 96.9%, for each. Whereas the bacteria recorded the lowest resistance rate to the antibiotic Meropenem, which reached 48.4%, while the other drugs showed diverse resistance, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Antibacterial agent susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* isolates.

Antibacterial agent	Resistance (%)	Intermediate (%)	Sensitive (%)
Piperacillin-Tazobactam	21 (63.63)	8 (24.24)	4 (12.12)
Cefepime	33 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Netilmicin	32(96.96)	0(0)	1(3.03)
Amikacin	29 (87.87)	3 (9.09)	1 (3.03)
Meropenem	16 (48.48)	4 (12.12)	13(39.39)
Norfloxacin	30 (90.90)	1 (3.03)	2 (6.06)
Ofloxacin	31(93.93)	1 (3.03)	1 (3.03)

3.3. Molecular detection of virulence factor genes in *P. aeruginosa* isolates.

Results of PCR about resistance genes showed that 33(100%), 33(100%), 29(87.87%), 29(87.87%),17(51.51%) and 9(27.27%) of *P. aeruginosa* isolates were harbored *lasB*, *algD*, *lasA*, *pilB*, *nan-1* and *pilA* genes, respectively (figure 1,2,3,4,5 and 6).

Figure 1: PCR products for *lasB* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Figure 2: PCR products for *algD* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Figure 3: PCR products for *lasA* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Figure 4: PCR products for *pilB* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Figure 5: PCR products for *nan-I* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

Figure 6: PCR products for *pilA* gene of *P. aeruginosa* isolates

4. Discussion

Pseudomonas aeruginosa causes hospital infections, especially in immunocompromised individuals. This work has shown that *P. aeruginosa* is highly resistant to most drugs, which is consistent with many studies.

The results of the current study showed a high prevalence of virulence factor genes among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates isolated from different clinical sources. This indicates a worrying indicator, especially the possibility of these genes being transferred to other bacterial strains. The results of molecular analysis support and reinforce the widespread prevalence and pathogenicity of *P. aeruginosa* in health institutions in the city of Najaf. In a local study conducted in hospitals in Babylon Governorate via [13], it was found that *P. aeruginosa* isolates were (71.75%) resistant to Norfloxacin, (64.12%) to Piperacillin-tazobactam, and (79.39%) to Amikacin, (93.90%) to Cefepime (93.90%) while their resistance to Meropenem was (81.68%).

In a local study conducted by [14] in Anbar, Iraq, to detect the virulence factor genes of *P. aeruginosa*, samples were collected from infected patients from the National Center for Educational Laboratories, the Educational Burns 84 Hospital, and the Ramadi Educational Hospital. It showed that the presence of the *algD* gene was 100%, and *pilA* was 92%, and *pilB* was 4%.

While globally also agreed with our results In a study conducted via [15] in Brazil, clinical samples were taken from different sources and it was found that the presence of the *pilA* gene was 14.1%, the *nan-1* gene was 14.1%, the *LasB* gene was 89.9%, the *pilB* gene was 27.3%, and the *algD* gene was 75.7%.

In a study conducted via [16] in Mazandaran Province, northern Iran, to detect the prevalence of virulence factor genes of *P. aeruginosa* isolated from patients admitted to educational and therapeutic hospitals in Iran, it was indicated that the percentage of *lasB* genes was (96%), while the prevalence of the *lasA* gene was (97%).

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